

Supplement for Symmetry Detection and Breaking in Cost-Optimal Numeric Planning[†]

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We present the detailed proof that the symmetry group of the colored numeric problem description graph (NPDG) is isomorphic to the group of numeric structural symmetries (NSS) of the same task. The definitions of NPDG and NSS appear in the original paper (Shleyfman, Kuroiwa, and Beck 2023).

Theorem 3. *Aut(NPDG_Π) and Aut(Π) are isomorphic.*

Proof. Let Π be a numeric planning task, with the corresponding $NPDG_{\Pi} = \langle N, E, \text{col} \rangle$. We start with the definition of the map $f : \text{Aut}(NPDG_{\Pi}) \rightarrow \text{Aut}(\Pi)$ that we aim to prove to be a bijection.

Let $f(\alpha) = l^{-1} \circ \alpha \circ l \in \text{Aut}(\Pi)$, where the map

$$l : \mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{A} \cup \left(\bigsqcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_p} \mathcal{D}(v) \right) \rightarrow N$$

is given by $l(x) \mapsto n_x$, with a slight abuse of notation $l(\langle v, d \rangle) = n_d^v$. Note that f is a homomorphism, i.e., $f(\alpha) \circ f(\beta) = f(\alpha \circ \beta)$.

First, we need to show that f is **well-defined**, i.e., $f(\alpha) \in \text{Aut}(\Pi)$. Since $\alpha \in \text{Aut}(NPDG_{\Pi})$ is color-, edge- and degree-preserving we have that the vertex sets $N_{\mathcal{V}_p}, N_{\mathcal{V}_n}, N_{\mathcal{A}}, N_{\Psi_n}, N_+, \bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_p} N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}, \bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_n} N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}$, and $\{n_G\}$ are all preserved under α . Specifically, $N_{\mathcal{V}_p}, N_{\mathcal{V}_n}$, and $\bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_p} N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}$ are preserved since, while being of the same color, each $n \in N_{\mathcal{V}_n}$ has zero neighbors of color 0, each $n \in N_{\mathcal{V}_p}$ has at least one neighbor of color 0 and an in-degree of magnitude zero, while $n \in \bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_p} N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}$ has at least one neighbor of color 0 and an in-degree that is at least one. All other sets differ due to different colors. Note also that since α is edge preserving we have that if $\alpha(n_v) = n_u$ then $\alpha(N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}) = N_{\mathcal{D}(u)}$. Vertices in N_+ must differ from the ones in N_{Ψ_n} under α , since each $n \in N_+$ has at least one outgoing neighbor of color 0, and the vertices in N_{Ψ_n} has none of these. Hence, we have that $f(\alpha)$ obeys the properties 1-3 of the definition of NSS.

Property 5 is preserved also due to edge preservice and the fact that $\alpha(n_G) = n_G$. Note that if $\langle v, d \rangle \in G_p$ then, by construction of $NPDG_{\Pi}$, we have that $(n_d^v, n_G) \in E$, thus $(\alpha(n_d^v), \alpha(n_G)) = (n_G, n_G) \in E$, which means that

$f(\alpha)(\langle v, d \rangle) \in G_p$. Now, let $\psi : \xi \triangleright 0 \in G_n$. Then, $(n_{\xi}^{\triangleright}, n_G) \in E$, and once again $(\alpha(n_{\xi}^{\triangleright}), n_G) \in E$. Note that for each $v \in \text{vars}(\xi)$ there is $w_v^{\xi} \in \text{nums}(\xi)$, and by construction of $NPDG_{\Pi}$ there are edges $(n_v, n_{w_v^{\xi}}^v), (n_{w_v^{\xi}}^v, n_{\xi}^{\triangleright}) \in E$. Since α is edge preserving, we have the path $(\alpha(n_v), \alpha(n_{w_v^{\xi}}^v), (\alpha(n_{w_v^{\xi}}^v), \alpha(n_{\xi}^{\triangleright})), (\alpha(n_{\xi}^{\triangleright}), n_G)) \in E$, thus the summand $w_v^{\xi} f(\alpha)(v)$ is a part of the expression $f(\alpha)(\xi) \triangleright 0$, since $\alpha(n_{w_v^{\xi}}^v)$ and $n_{w_v^{\xi}}^v$ must be of the same color, v and $f(\alpha)(v)$ have the same multiple in ξ and $f(\alpha)(\xi)$, respectively. And since α is in-degree preserving, the number of summands in ξ is equal to the number of summands in $f(\alpha)(\xi)$. Hence, $f(\alpha)(\xi)$ is well-defined in terms of NSS, and $f(\alpha)(\xi) \triangleright 0 \in G$. Therefore, $f(\alpha)(G) \subseteq G$. To show the converse we need to recall that $\alpha^{-1} \in \text{Aut}(NPDG_{\Pi})$ and f is a homomorphism.

To prove property 4, we need to show that $f(\alpha)(h(a)) = h(f(\alpha)(a))$ for each $h \in \{\text{pre}_n, \text{pre}_p, \text{eff}_n, \text{eff}_p, \text{cost}\}$. This property on preconditions is obtained exactly as Property 5, where the node n_G is replaced with the nodes n_a and $n_{f(\alpha)(a)}$. The proof for effects is similar, but requires us to look at the nodes n_{ξ}^{\dagger} , where the only outgoing edge is pointed towards a node that represents a numeric variable. We omit the full proof here, since it repeats almost verbatim the one given in the previous paragraph.

For the **injectivity** of f , consider $\alpha, \beta \in \text{Aut}(NPDG_{\Pi})$:

$$\begin{aligned} f(\alpha) = f(\beta) &\implies l^{-1} \circ \alpha \circ l = l^{-1} \circ \beta \circ l \implies \\ \alpha(n) = \beta(n) &\text{ for all } n \in N_{\mathcal{V}} \cup N_{\mathcal{A}} \cup \bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_p} N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last implication follows from the fact that l is bijective. To show that f is injective, we need to show that $\alpha(n) = \beta(n)$ for all $n \in N$. Thus, assume in contradiction that there is $n \in N$ such that $\alpha(n) \neq \beta(n)$. This n is either n_G or lies in $N_{\Xi} \cup \bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_n} N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}$. Since n_G has its own color, it is a fixed under permutations in $\text{Aut}(NPDG_{\Pi})$. Since f is well-defined we have that $f(\alpha), f(\beta) \in \text{Aut}(\Pi)$, thus for $n_w^v \in \bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_n} N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(n_w^v) = n_w^{f(\alpha)(v)} &= n_w^{f(\beta)(v)} = \beta(n_w^v), \text{ and} \\ \alpha(n_{\xi}^{\dagger}) = n_{f(\alpha)(\xi)}^{\dagger} &= n_{f(\beta)(\xi)}^{\dagger} = \beta(n_{\xi}^{\dagger}) \text{ for } n_{\xi}^{\dagger} \in N_{\Xi}. \end{aligned}$$

[†] See Shleyfman, Kuroiwa, and Beck (2023)

Lastly, to show that f is **surjective**, we need to prove that $f^{-1}(\sigma)$ is in $Aut(NPDG_{\Pi})$, when σ is an NSS. We extend this inverse as follows

$$f^{-1}(\sigma)(n) = \begin{cases} n_{\sigma(x)} & \text{if } n = n_x \in N_{\mathcal{V}_p} \cup N_{\mathcal{V}_n} \cup N_{\mathcal{A}} \\ n_{\sigma(\langle v, d \rangle)} & \text{if } n = n_d^v = n_{\langle v, d \rangle} \in \bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_p}, \\ n_w^{\sigma(v)} & \text{if } n = n_w^v \in \bigcup_{v \in \mathcal{V}_n}, \\ n_{\sigma(\xi)}^{\dagger} & \text{if } n = n_{\xi}^{\dagger} \in N_{\Xi} \wedge \dagger \in \{+, \geq, >\}, \\ n_G & \text{if } n = n_G. \end{cases}$$

The extended function $f^{-1}(\sigma)$ is well-defined, i.e., all vertices that involve σ in their indices do exist in $NPDG_{\Pi}$. To show this, we note that by definition σ is a permutation on variables, actions, and $\sigma(\langle v, d \rangle) \in \mathcal{D}(\sigma(v))$. Moreover, for each n_w^v there is $\xi \in \Xi$, such that $w \in num_s(\xi)$. We saw that for an NSS it holds that $\sigma(\Xi) = \Xi$. Hence, $\sigma(\xi) \in \Xi$, thus, $w\sigma(v)$ is a summand in $\sigma(\xi)$. Lastly, to show that $n_{\sigma(\xi)}^{\dagger} \in NPDG_{\Pi}$, note that $\sigma(\Xi) = \Xi$ and NSS preserves linear conditions and effects.

Next, note that, by construction, f^{-1} is a homomorphism, since for $\sigma, \sigma' \in Aut(\Pi)$ it holds $f^{-1}(\sigma \circ \sigma') = f^{-1}(\sigma) \circ f^{-1}(\sigma')$. Moreover, for the identity element $id_{\Pi} \in Aut(\Pi)$ it holds that $e := f^{-1}(id_{\Pi})$ is an identity element in $Aut(NPDG_{\Pi})$. Let $\alpha := f^{-1}(\sigma)$, it is invertible, hence, a permutation since:

$$\alpha \circ f^{-1}(\sigma^{-1}) = f^{-1}(\sigma) \circ f^{-1}(\sigma^{-1}) = f^{-1}(\sigma \circ \sigma^{-1}) = f^{-1}(id_{\Pi}) = e \implies \alpha^{-1} = f^{-1}(\sigma^{-1}).$$

Next, we need to show that α is edge- and color-preserving. We begin with color preservation.

- $\alpha(N_{\mathcal{V}_p}) = N_{\mathcal{V}_p}$, $\alpha(N_{\mathcal{V}_n}) = N_{\mathcal{V}_n}$, and $\alpha(N_{\mathcal{A}}) = N_{\mathcal{A}}$ since $\sigma(\mathcal{V}_p) = \mathcal{V}_p$, $\sigma(\mathcal{V}_n) = \mathcal{V}_n$, and $\sigma(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{A}$, respectively. All vertices in $N_{\mathcal{V}}$ are of the same color. On action vertices, $n_a \in N_{\mathcal{A}}$, the colors are preserved due to

$$\begin{aligned} \text{col}(\alpha(n_a)) &= \text{col}(n_{\sigma(a)}) = \text{ord}(\text{cost}(\sigma(a))) = \\ &= \text{ord}(\text{cost}(a)) = \text{col}(n_a). \end{aligned}$$

- For a variable $v \in \mathcal{V}_p$ we have $\sigma(\mathcal{D}(v)) = \mathcal{D}(\sigma(v))$. Thus, $\alpha(N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}) = N_{\mathcal{D}(\sigma(v))}$. Thus, α fixes the color on the propositional domains vertices.
- Let $v \in \mathcal{V}_n$, and $n_w^v \in N_{\mathcal{D}(v)}$, then

$$\text{col}(\alpha(n_w^v)) = \text{col}(n_w^{\sigma(v)}) = \text{ord}(w) = \text{col}(n_w^v).$$

- For $n_{\xi}^{\dagger} \in N_{\Xi}$ it holds that $\alpha(n_{\xi}^{\dagger}) = n_{\sigma(\xi)}^{\dagger} \in N_{\Xi}$, and

$$\text{col}(\alpha(n_{\xi}^{\dagger})) = \text{col}(n_{\sigma(\xi)}^{\dagger}) = |\mathcal{C}_{\Pi}| + \text{rel}(\dagger) = \text{col}(n_{\xi}^{\dagger}).$$

- Trivially, $\text{col}(\alpha(n_G)) = \text{col}(n_G)$.

Thus, we have that α is color preserving vertex permutation. The last property for α being a color-preserving automorphism, is edge-preservance, $(n, n') \in E \iff (\alpha(n), \alpha(n')) \in E$.

The “ \implies ” part of this property follows from a meticulous application of NSS properties 1-5 to

$$E = E_{\mathcal{V}_p} \cup E_{\mathcal{V}_n} \cup E_{\Xi} \cup E_{\mathcal{A}} \cup E_G.$$

We omit the full proof here since it is straightforward and repetitive. Overall, the edges of $NPDG_{\Pi}$ correspond to element membership in sets, e.g., the edge (n_d^v, n_G) corresponds to $\langle v, d \rangle \in G$, $(n_w^v, n_{\xi}^{\dagger})$ to $w_v \in num_s(\xi)$ and $u += \xi \in \text{eff}_n(a)$ for some $a \in \mathcal{A}$ and $v \in \mathcal{V}_n$. This part of the proof is similar to the proofs of Thm. 5 in Sievers et al. (2019) and Thm. 4.4 in Shleyfman (2020).

Briefly, the edges in $E_{\mathcal{V}_p}$ are preserved due to properties 1 and 2, E_{Ξ} and $E_{\mathcal{A}}$ are preserved due to properties 3-4, and E_G is preserved due to property 5. E_{Ξ} is preserved since $\sigma(\Xi) = \Xi$. The “ \Leftarrow ” part holds since α is invertible. \square

References

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